

**Rapoport's rule explains the range size distribution of butterflies along the Eastern
Himalayan elevation gradient**

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TABLE S1

Table S1.1. Observed richness, estimated richness, rarefied richness and number of individuals butterflies along with effort for each elevational zone along in Rangeet Valley, Eastern Himalaya.

Study Sites	Elevation midpoint (m)	Effort (point count)	Observed species richness	Chao1	Jack1	Rarefied richness	No of individuals
T1	350	130	121	145.76	155.73	115.03	800
T2	500	120	118	173.89	169.57	113.77	497
T3	650	120	80	107.2	104.79	77.84	364
T4	800	110	69	99.99	95.75	69	291
T5	950	120	79	89.56	100.82	77.21	358
T6	1150	120	49	64.46	68.83	47.35	179
T7	1350	110	58	105.01	85.75	58	201
T8	1550	110	36	44.18	47.89	36	123
T9	1700	110	56	118.67	84.74	56	189
T10	1900	120	31	42.04	43.89	29.87	112
T11	2100	120	27	28.65	31.96	26.55	129
T12	2300	110	24	26.48	29.95	24	113
T13	2500	110	12	12	12.99	12	96
T14	2700	120	11	11.99	12.98	10.83	69
T15	2900	120	10	10.25	11.98	9.81	54
T16	3100	110	8	8	8.88	8	28

Table S1.2 : Details of the butterfly species recorded during the study in Rangeet Valley, Sikkim, Eastern Himalaya, and their elevational range profile. The study included various butterfly family sub-groups such as Nymphalidae, Papilionidae, Hesperidae, Lycaenidae, Pieridae, and Riodinidae. Based on larval host diet breadth butterflies were categorised as monophagous species (feeding on a single genus of host plant), oligophagous species (feeding on plants within the same family), and polyphagous species (larvae feeding on a wide range of plants). The butterflies were further grouped into Palearctic, Oriental, Afro-tropical, and global categories based on their affinity to specific realms or multiple realms.

(OR- Oriental species; PA- Palearctic; GL- Global; SR- Small Range; LR- Large Range; MO-Monophagous; OL- Oligophagous; PL- Polyphagous).

Scientific Name	Common Name	Family	Biogeographic Affinity	Feeding Guild	Lowest elevation where species detected (m)	Highest elevation where species detected (m)	Elevational range (m)	Elevational mid-point (m)
<i>Arhopala abseus</i>	Aberrant Oakblue	Lycaenidae	OR	MO	300	400	100	350
<i>Halpe filda</i>	Absent Ace	Hesperidae	OR	OL	300	1200	900	750
<i>Lethe chandica</i>	Angled Red Forester	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1100	1200	100	1150
<i>Spalgis epius</i>	Apefly	Lycaenidae	AT	Carnivorous	450	700	250	575
<i>Arhopala sp</i>	Arhopalasp	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	900	1000	100	950
<i>Lethe kansa</i>	Bamboo Forester	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Lethe confusa</i>	Banded Treebrown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Lethe maitrya</i>	Barred Woodbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	2250	3150	900	2700
<i>Prosotas lutea</i>	Bhutea Lineblue	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	1100	1200	100	1150
<i>Rohana paristas</i>	Black Prince	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	550	250	425
<i>Matapa saivarna</i>	Black Veined Redeye	Hesperidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Athyma ranga</i>	Blackvein Sergeant	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	850	550	575
<i>Euthalia telchinia</i>	Blue Baron	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	900	1000	100	950
<i>Bassarona durga</i>	Blue Duke	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1300	1400	100	1350

<i>Papilio polymnestor</i>	Blue Mormon	Papilionidae	GL	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Papilio arcturus</i>	Blue Peacock	Papilionidae	GL	OL	1650	1750	100	1700
<i>Elymnias patna</i>	Blue Striped Palmfly	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Symbrenthia niphanda</i>	Blue Tailed Jester	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1300	1950	650	1625
<i>Chliaria kina</i>	Blue Tit	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	1650	2350	700	2000
<i>Curetis bulis</i>	Bright Sunbeam	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	300	850	550	575
<i>Neptis sankara</i>	Broad Banded Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	1500	1600	100	1550
<i>Neptis narayana</i>	Broadstick Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	2050	2350	300	2200
<i>Rohana parvata</i>	Brown Prince	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	2050	2150	100	2100
<i>Arhopala centaurus</i>	Centuar Oakblue	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	700	400	500
<i>Odontoptilum angulata</i>	Chestnut Angle	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	450	550	100	500
<i>Lambrix salsala</i>	Chestnut Bob	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Parantica sita</i>	Chestnut Tiger	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	2350	2050	1325
<i>Appias lyncida</i>	Chocolate Albatross	Pieridae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Junonia iphita</i>	Chocolate Pansy	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Hestina nama</i>	Circe	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Spindasis yama</i>	Club Silverline	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	1100	1200	100	1150
<i>Athyma nefte</i>	Colour Sergeant	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	450	550	100	500
<i>Moduza procris</i>	Commander	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	550	250	425
<i>Surendra quercetorum</i>	Common Acacia Blue	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Appias albina</i>	Common Albatross	Pieridae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Hasora badra</i>	Common Awl	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Hasora chromus</i>	Common Banded Awl	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	1300	1400	100	1350
<i>Euthalia aconthea</i>	Common Baron	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350

<i>Atrophaneura varuna</i>	Common Batwing	Papilionidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Troides helena</i>	Common Birdwing	Papilionidae	OR	MO	450	1200	750	825
<i>Graphium sarpedon</i>	Common Blue Bottle	Papilionidae	OR	PL	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Mycalesis perseus</i>	Common Bushbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Ariadne merione</i>	Common Castor	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Jamides celeno</i>	Common Cerulean	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	1200	900	750
<i>Euploea core</i>	Common Crow	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Oriens gola</i>	Common Darlet	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Discophora sondaica</i>	Common Duffer	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Tanaecia julii</i>	Common Earl	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Catapsilia pomona</i>	Common Emigrant	Pieridae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Melanitis leda</i>	Common Evening Brown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Yptima baldus</i>	Common Fivering	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Rapala nissa</i>	Common Flash	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	600	1950	1350	1275
<i>Lethe isana</i>	Common Forester	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	2050	2550	500	2300
<i>Ypthima huebneri</i>	Common Fouring	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	450	1400	950	925
<i>Eurema hecabe</i>	Common Grass Yellow	Pieridae	GL	OL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Cepora nerissa</i>	Common Gull	Pieridae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Acytolepis puspa</i>	Common Hedge Blue	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	1950	1650	1125
<i>Cheritra freja</i>	Common Imperial	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Graphium doson</i>	Common Jay	Papilionidae	OR	PL	300	550	250	425
<i>Symbrenthia lilaea</i>	Common Jester	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Delias eucharis</i>	Common Jezebel	Pieridae	OR	PL	1300	1400	100	1350

<i>Pantoporia hordonia</i>	Common Lascar	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Phalanta phalantha</i>	Common Leopard	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Prosotas nora</i>	Common Lineblue	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	600	1050	450	825
<i>Cyrestis thyodamas</i>	Common Map	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1950	1650	1125
<i>Cherosonesia risa</i>	Common Maplet	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	400	100	350
<i>Papilioclytia</i>	Common Mime	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Papilio polytes</i>	Common Mormon	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Elymnias hypermnestra</i>	Common Palmfly	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	550	250	425
<i>Papilio bianor</i>	Common Peacock	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Papilio castor</i>	Common Raven	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	550	250	425
<i>Lethe mekara</i>	Common Red Forester	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	600	1400	800	1000
<i>Matapa aria</i>	Common Redeye	Hesperiidae	OR	MO	450	550	100	500
<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	Common Rose	Papilionidae	OR	OL	300	850	550	575
<i>Neptis hylas</i>	Common Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Aulocera swaha</i>	Common Satyr	Nymphalidae	PA	OL	2650	3150	500	2900
<i>Athyma perius</i>	Common Sergeant	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1950	1650	1125
<i>Sarangesada sahara</i>	Common Small Flat	Hesperiidae	African	OL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Catapaecilma major</i>	Common Tinsel	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	450	550	100	500
<i>Hypolycaena erylus</i>	Common Tit	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	2550	2250	1425
<i>Byasa polyeuctes</i>	Common Windmill	Papilionidae	OR	OL	450	1750	1300	1100
<i>Lethe sidonis</i>	Common Woodbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	1850	3150	1300	2500
<i>Cirrochroa tyche</i>	Common Yeamon	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Pelopidas conjuncta</i>	Conjoined Swift	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	1100	1200	100	1150

<i>Deudorix epijarbas</i>	Cornelian	Lycaenidae	AT	PL	450	700	250	575
<i>Neptis soma</i>	Creamy Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1000	700	650
<i>Vindulaerota</i>	Cruiser	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	550	250	425
<i>Hypolimnas misippus</i>	Daniad Eggfly	Nymphalidae	GL	PL	300	700	400	500
<i>Trimumala septentrionis</i>	Dark Blue Tiger	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1950	1650	1125
<i>Mycalesis mineus</i>	Dark Branded Bush Brown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	450	1950	1500	1200
<i>Jamides bochus</i>	Dark Cerulean	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	300	850	550	575
<i>Colias fieldii</i>	Dark Clouded Yellow	Pieridae	PA	OL	2250	3150	900	2700
<i>Melanitis phedima</i>	Dark Evening Brown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	450	1400	950	925
<i>Zizeeria karsandra</i>	Dark Grass Blue	Lycaenidae	AT	PL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Abisara echerius</i>	Dark Judy	Riodinidae	OR	MO	450	2550	2100	1500
<i>Korutaiolos butleri</i>	Dark Velvet Bob	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Potanthus sp</i>	Dart Sp	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	300	1200	900	750
<i>Neope yama</i>	Dusky Labyrinth	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	2850	2950	100	2900
<i>Gerosis phisara</i>	Dusky Yellow Breasted Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	MO	450	550	100	500
<i>Neptis pseudovikasi</i>	False Dingy Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	450	550	100	500
<i>Boaris pagana</i>	Figure of 8 Swift	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	1300	1750	450	1525
<i>Zeltus amasa</i>	Fluffy Tit	Lycaenidae	OR	MO	300	1000	700	650
<i>Taraka hamada</i>	Forest Perriot	Lycaenidae	OR	Carnivorous	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Catochrysops strabo</i>	Forget Me Not	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	450	550	100	500
<i>Pseudocoladenia dan</i>	Fulvous Pied Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Euthalia lubentina</i>	Gaudy Baron	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350

<i>Graphium colanthes</i>	Glassy Blue Bottel	Papilionidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Parantica aglea</i>	Glassy Tiger	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	1950	1650	1125
<i>Troides aeacus</i>	Golden Birdwing	Papilionidae	OR	OL	1650	2150	500	1900
<i>Heliophorus brahma</i>	Golden Sapphire	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	1100	2150	1050	1625
<i>Hypolimnas bolina</i>	Great Eggfly	Nymphalidae	GL	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Graphium eurypylus</i>	Great Jay	Papilionidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Papilio memnon</i>	Great Mormon	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	2150	1850	1225
<i>Hebomia glaucippe</i>	Great Orange Tip	Pieridae	OR	OL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Byasa dasarada</i>	Great Windmill	Papilionidae	OR	MO	450	1750	1300	1100
<i>Neptis radha</i>	Great Yellow Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	1650	2150	500	1900
<i>Sumalia daraxa</i>	Green Commodore	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1650	2150	500	1900
<i>Arhopala eumolphus</i>	Green Oakblue	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Junonia atlites</i>	Grey Pansy	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Aeromachus sghora</i>	Grey Scrub Hopper	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	750	1750	1000	1250
<i>Delias belladonna</i>	Hill Jezebel	Pieridae	OR	MO	900	1750	850	1325
<i>Ypthima sakra</i>	Himalayan Fivering	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1100	2150	1050	1625
<i>Symbrenthia brabira</i>	Himalayan Jester	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Issoria isaaea</i>	Himalayan Queen Fritillary	Nymphalidae	PA	MO	2650	3150	500	2900
<i>Athyma opalina</i>	Himalayan Sergeant	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1300	2350	1050	1825
<i>Celaenorrhinus munda</i>	Himalayan Spotted Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	1650	1750	100	1700
<i>Neptis nycteus</i>	Hockey Stick Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	2250	2350	100	2300

<i>Pieris Canidia</i>	Indian Cabbage White	Pieridae	PA	OL	300	2950	2650	1625
<i>Argynnis hyperbius</i>	Indian Fritillary	Nymphalidae	PA	PL	450	1600	1150	1025
<i>Charaxes bharata</i>	Indian Nawab	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Mimathyma ambica</i>	Indian Purple Emperor	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	750	850	100	800
<i>Vanessa inidca</i>	Indian Red Admiral	Nymphalidae	GL	PL	300	2350	2050	1325
<i>Aglais cashmiriensis</i>	Indian Tortoiseshell	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	3150	2850	1725
<i>Lebadea martha</i>	Knight	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Pieris brassicae</i>	Large Cabbge White	Pieridae	PA	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Arhopala amantes</i>	Large Oakblue	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Argynnis childreni</i>	Large Silverstripe	Nymphalidae	PA	MO	750	1950	1200	1350
<i>Raphicera satricus</i>	Large Twany Wall	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	2250	2350	100	2300
<i>Cirrochroa aoris</i>	Large Yeoman	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Junonia lemonias</i>	Lemon Pansy	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	850	550	575
<i>Neptis nashona</i>	Less Rich Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	450	550	100	500
<i>Zizina otis</i>	Lesser Grass Blue	Lycaenidae	None	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Cepora nadina</i>	Lesser Gull	Pieridae	OR	MO	300	550	250	425
<i>Dodona dipoea</i>	Lesser Punch	Riodinidae	OR	OL	1850	2350	500	2100
<i>Borbo bevani</i>	Lesser Rice Swift	Hesperiidae	African	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Mycalesis francisca</i>	Lilacine Bushbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	450	1750	1300	1100
<i>Lethe sura</i>	Liliacfork	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	1850	1950	100	1900
<i>Cigraitis lohita</i>	Long Banded Silverline	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Euploeaalgea</i>	Long Branded Blue Crow	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	600	700	100	650

<i>Mycalesis visala</i>	Long Branded Bushbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Megisba malaya</i>	Malayan	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	850	550	575
<i>Charana mandarinus</i>	Mandrain Blue	Lycaenidae	OR	MO	600	1000	400	800
<i>Orsotrioena medus</i>	Medus Brown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	600	700	100	650
<i>Jamides alecto</i>	Metallic Cerulean	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	450	1600	1150	1025
<i>Dodona ouida</i>	Mixed Punch	Riodinidae	OR	MO	1650	2550	900	2100
<i>Catopsiliapyranthe</i>	Mottled Emigrant	Pieridae	OR	PL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Tagiades parra</i>	Multi-Spotted Snow Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	300	550	250	425
<i>Pseudocoladenia dan</i>	Naga Pied Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	1650	1750	100	1700
<i>Yptima newara</i>	Newara Threering	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1100	1200	100	1150
<i>Eurema andersoni</i>	One Spot Grass Yellow	Pieridae	GL	OL	300	850	550	575
<i>Burara jaina</i>	Orange Awlet	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	450	550	100	500
<i>Kallimainachus</i>	Orange Oakleaf	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Athyma cama</i>	Orange Staff Sergeant	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Chliaria othona</i>	Orchid Tit	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	300	550	250	425
<i>Baoris farri</i>	Paint Brush Swift	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	1650	1750	100	1700
<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	Painted Lady	Nymphalidae	GL	PL	600	3150	2550	1875
<i>Pseudozizeeria maha</i>	Pale Grass Blue	Lycaenidae	None	PL	450	1400	950	925
<i>Neptis zaida</i>	Pale Green Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	1100	1200	100	1150
<i>Udara dilecta</i>	Pale Hedge Blue	Lycaenidae	OR	MO	300	2350	2050	1325
<i>Charaxes arja</i>	Pallid Nawab	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	450	1000	550	725
<i>Papilio paris</i>	Paris Peacock	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	1200	900	750
<i>Parnara sp</i>	Parnara sp	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	750	850	100	800
<i>Herona marathus</i>	Pasha	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	450	550	100	500

<i>Lampides boeticus</i>	Pea Blue	Lycaenidae	None	OL	600	3150	2550	1875
<i>Celastrina lavendularis</i>	Plain Hedge Blue	Lycaenidae	PA	OL	1100	1200	100	1150
<i>Appias indra</i>	Plain Puffin	Pieridae	OR	PL	1100	1200	100	1150
<i>Neptis cartica</i>	Plain Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Stibochiona nicea</i>	Popinjay	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	2150	1850	1225
<i>Euthalia monina</i>	Powdered Baron	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Heliophorus tamu</i>	Powdery Green Sapphire	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	2050	2350	300	2200
<i>Leptos ianina</i>	Psyche	Pieridae	AT	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Zemerus flegyas</i>	Punchinello	Riodinidae	OR	MO	300	2150	1850	1225
<i>Zographetus satwa</i>	Purple and Gold Flitter	Hesperiidae	OR	MO	600	1000	400	800
<i>Heliophorusepicles</i>	Purple Sapphire	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Celaenorrhinus ratna</i>	Ratna Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	2050	2150	100	2100
<i>Delias pasithoe</i>	Red Base Jezebel	Pieridae	OR	MO	300	550	250	425
<i>Papilio alcmenor</i>	Red Breast	Papilionidae	GL	MO	450	550	100	500
<i>Papilio helenus</i>	Red Helen	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	2150	1850	1225
<i>Cethosia biblis</i>	Red Lacewing	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	600	1950	1350	1275
<i>Delias descombesi</i>	Red Spot Jezebel	Pieridae	OR	MO	450	1000	550	725
<i>Notocrypta curvifascia</i>	Restricted Demon	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Celaenorrhinus putra</i>	Restricted Spotted Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	1300	1400	100	1350
<i>Erionota torus</i>	Rounded Palm-redeye	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	1300	1400	100	1350
<i>Neptis sappho</i>	Rusty Sailer	Nymphalidae	PA	OL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Lethe dura</i>	Scarce Liliackfork	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1850	1950	100	1900
<i>Lethe siderea</i>	Scarce Woodbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	2250	2350	100	2300

<i>Mimathyma chevana</i>	Sergeant Emperor	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	450	550	100	500
<i>Abrota ganga</i>	Sergeant Major	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1300	1400	100	1350
<i>Pseudocoladenia fatua</i>	Sikkim Pied Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	450	1950	1500	1200
<i>Maneca bhotea</i>	Slate Royal	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	2650	2750	100	2700
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i>	Small Branded Swift	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Eurema brigitta</i>	Small Grass Yellow	Pieridae	GL	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Lethe nicetella</i>	Small Woodbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	2650	2750	100	2700
<i>Nepti smiah</i>	Small Yellow Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Oriens golodies</i>	Smaller Dartlet	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	450	700	250	575
<i>Papilioprotenor</i>	Spangle	Papilionidae	GL	OL	300	1750	1450	1025
<i>Appiaslalage</i>	Spot Puffin	Pieridae	OR	PL	450	2550	2100	1500
<i>Euremalaeta</i>	Spotless Grass Yellow	Pieridae	GL	OL	1650	1750	100	1700
<i>Notocrypta feisthameli</i>	Spotted Demon	Hesperiidae	OR	MO	1100	2150	1050	1625
<i>Symbrenthia hypselis</i>	Spotted Jester	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	450	1200	750	825
<i>Prioneristhestylis</i>	Spotted Sawtooth	Pieridae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500
<i>Tagiades menaka</i>	Spotted Snow Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Athyma selenophora</i>	Staff Sergeant	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	550	250	425
<i>Polyura dolon</i>	Stately Nawab	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Lethe verma</i>	Straight Banded Treebrown	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	450	2150	1700	1300
<i>Orthomiella pontis</i>	Straightwing Blue	Lycaenidae	PA	MO	1850	2350	500	2100
<i>Appias olferna</i>	Striped Albatross	Pieridae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Euploea mulciber</i>	Striped Blue Crow	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	2150	1850	1225
<i>Capila jayadeva</i>	Striped Dawnfly	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500

<i>Dodona adonira</i>	Striped Punch	Riodinidae	OR	MO	2050	2350	300	2200
<i>Danaus genutica</i>	Striped Tiger	Nymphalidae	GL	PL	450	1750	1300	1100
<i>Neptis clinia</i>	Sullied Sailer	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Pseudergolis wedah</i>	Tabby	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	1650	1750	100	1700
<i>Graphium agamemnon</i>	Tailed Jay	Papilionidae	OR	PL	300	1200	900	750
<i>Dodona eugenes</i>	Tailed Punch	Riodinidae	OR	MO	2250	2550	300	2400
<i>Lethe sinorix</i>	Tailed Red Forester	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	450	2150	1700	1300
<i>Dercas verhuelli</i>	Tailed Sulphur	Pieridae	OR	MO	450	1200	750	825
<i>Flos areste</i>	Tailless Plushblue	Lycaenidae	OR	OL	1500	1600	100	1550
<i>Eurema blanda</i>	Three Spot Grass Yellow	Pieridae	GL	OL	300	1400	1100	850
<i>Orinoma damaris</i>	Tiger brown	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	1100	2150	1050	1625
<i>Ochus subvittatus</i>	Tiger Hopper	Hesperiidae	OR	MO	600	850	250	725
<i>Gandaca harina</i>	Tree Yellow	Pieridae	OR	PL	300	1000	700	650
<i>Coladenia indrani</i>	Tri Coloured Pied Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	300	400	100	350
<i>Graphium chironides</i>	Viened Jay	Papilionidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Neope pulaha</i>	Viened Labyrinth	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1850	2350	500	2100
<i>Aeromachus stigmata</i>	Viened Scrub Hooper	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	1100	1750	650	1425
<i>Tagiades litigiosa</i>	Water Snow Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	PL	300	850	550	575
<i>Mycalesis anaxias</i>	White Bar Bushbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	300	400	100	350
<i>Euthalia phemius</i>	White Edged Blue Baron	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	450	700	250	575
<i>Mycalesis mestra</i>	White Edged Bush Brown	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	1300	1400	100	1350
<i>Polytremis discreta</i>	White Fringed Swift	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	300	400	100	350
<i>Gerosis sinca</i>	White Yellow Breasted Flat	Hesperiidae	OR	OL	450	550	100	500

<i>Teligna malsara</i>	White-Line Bushbrown	Nymphalidae	AT	OL	450	1400	950	925
<i>Loxura atymnus</i>	Yamfly	Lycaenidae	OR	PL	300	1600	1300	950
<i>Acraea issoria</i>	Yellow Coster	Nymphalidae	AT	OL	750	1000	250	875
<i>Papilio nephelus</i>	Yellow Helen	Papilionidae	GL	OL	450	1400	950	925
<i>Delias agostina</i>	Yellow Jezebel	Pieridae	OR	PL	450	1400	950	925
<i>Ixias pryene</i>	Yellow Orange Tip	Pieridae	OR	MO	300	1000	700	650
<i>Neorina hilda</i>	Yellow Owl	Nymphalidae	OR	PL	2250	2350	100	2300
<i>Junonia hierta</i>	Yellow Pansy	Nymphalidae	OR	OL	600	1000	400	800
<i>Polytremis eltola</i>	Yellow Spot Swift	Hesperiidae	OR	MO	300	1950	1650	1125
<i>Lethe nicetas</i>	Yellow Woodbrown	Nymphalidae	OR	MO	2850	2950	100	2900
<i>Leptotes plinius</i>	Zebra Blue	Lycaenidae	GL	PL	900	1000	100	950

Figure S1: Species accumulation curves of butterflies observed at different elevations (in m above sea level) in Rangeet Valley, Sikkim, Eastern Himalaya. The blue line is observed richness, the red line the Chao1 and green dotted line the Jackknife 1 estimates. x axis= Point counts, y axis= Species richness.